

Education Infrastructure Requirement in Dang District

Parin Manishbhai Patel

PG Student, Master of Planning, Bhaikaka Centre for Human Settlements (APIED),
Vallabh Vidhyanagar, Gujarat, India

How to cite this paper: Parin Manishbhai Patel "Education Facility requirement in Dang district" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-5, August 2019, pp.30-33, <https://doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd23720>

ABSTRACT

Education is a constitutional directive. Article 45 of the Directive Principles of the constitution urges all state to provide 'free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age of fourteen years' within a period of ten years from the commencement of the constitution. Right to education has been recognized as fundamental right in 83rd constitutional amendment, even then the goal of universal education for all has remained distant dream. The status of education is one of the key indicators of socio-economic development and employment opportunities largely depend on the level of education. This paper shows status of existing education facility and gap analysis in the Dangs district of Gujarat state.

KEYWORDS: Education, Dang, Planning, Gap, Analysis, Tribal

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

Education is the key that will allow many other Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to be achieved. When people are able to get quality education they can break from the cycle of poverty. Education therefore helps to reduce inequalities and to reach gender equality. It also empowers people everywhere to live more healthy and sustainable lives. Education is also crucial to fostering tolerance between people and contributes to more peaceful societies.¹

Literacy is one of the important characteristics of the demography. The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO] defines literacy as "ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate, compute and use printed and written materials associated with varying contexts. Literacy involves a continuum of learning in enabling individuals to achieve their goals, to develop their knowledge and potential, and to participate fully in their community and wider society." Census of India defines literates as 'A person aged 7 years and above who can both read and write with understanding in any language has been taken as literate. It is not necessary for a person to have received any formal education or passed any minimum educational standard for being treated as literate. People who were blind and could read in Braille are treated to be literates'.²

¹ <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/Goal-4.pdf>

² https://www.academia.edu/2344618/Status_of_Primary_Education_A_Case_Study_of_The_Dangs_District_in_Gujarat

INTRODUCTION

Education is the process of instruction aimed at an all-round development of individuals, providing the necessary tools and knowledge to understand and participate in day to day activities of today's world. It dispels ignorance and boosts moral values of the individuals. Education is the only wealth which cannot be robbed. It builds character, provides strength of mind and increases knowledge.

Aim

To study the current status of education facility and providing required facility as per the standards and specification.

Objectives

- To understand past and current scenario of the education facility.
- To study the standard norms for provision the education facility.
- To recommend and proposal for required education facility.

Literature review

Universal primary education is a constitutional directive. Article 45 of the Directive Principles of the constitution urges all state to provide 'free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age of fourteen years' within a period of ten years from the commencement of the constitution. In this paper author examined the status of primary education in the Dangs district. Author also narrate that attempts have been made by the government and different voluntary agencies to promote education among tribal groups. Author had listed down all in education facility available in the Dang district as per year 2007. After listing down all the school author had also given list of facilities available at school level. (Rami, 2012)

The researcher has accepted the present study on the subject as Primary Education in Dangs district. Dang district is a tribal area. The percentage of tribal people in this district is

very high as much as 93.96%. Here tribal people live with their unique specialty. The geographical situation of this district in the main hindrance of many problems in importing primary education. The status of poverty in local people is very high which also lends to obstruction in development of primary education. Objectives of the researcher are together information about the history of primary education of Dang District, to conduct a comparative study, of physical of physical administrative and economic matters of Primary schools run by trust, residential school (Ashramshala) rudy district Panchayat Govt. & residential school and Private residential schools run by trust. Researcher had given other practical suggestions for the promotion of future development of primary education of Dang. (Deshmukh, 2016)

Standards for education facility:

Table 1: Norms for education facility

Facility	Requirement (URDPFI/Planning commission)
Anganwadi	Each or Per 2500 population
Primary School	Each Per 2500 population
Secondary School	Per 7,500 population
Higher Secondary School	Per 15,000 Population
College	Per 125,000 Population
Tech. Training Institute	Per 100000 Population
Agriculture Research Centre	Per 100000 Population

(Source: Planning commission, URDPFI guideline; Vol = 1; 2014)

Methodology

Figure 1: Methodology

About the Dangs district

The Dangs district is located in the southern part of the Gujarat state. To the north and west of Dangs district lies Surat and Navsari districts of Gujarat whereas to its east and south are the districts of the Maharashtra state. The district of Dangs lies between 20.39° to 21.5° North latitudes and 72.29° to 73.51° East longitudes.³ The Bombay State was bifurcated on 1st May, 1960 and separate state of Gujarat and Maharashtra were formed. The Dangs district became a part of the Gujarat State and placed under the administrative control of the Collector of Surat. The area covered by this district is 1,766.00 sq. km i.e. it covers 0.90% of total geographical area of Gujarat. Physiography of Lower Dang region is characterized by low hills with an altitude ranging from 560 and 590 meters above M.S.L. Physiography of Upper Dang region is a hilly tract having thick forest cover. The elevation of this region varies between 675 and 1290 meters above M.S.L. The Dangs district is essentially a mountainous tract covered with dense forest which occupy 53 percent of its total area of Dang district.

Figure 2: Location of the Dang district (Source: Author)

The Dangs district is comprised of 311 villages and has an area of 1764 sq. km. Dang district is having three taluka – Ahwa, Subir and Waghai. Ahwa taluka is the headquarters of the Dang district. The Dangs district population constituted 0.38 percent of total Gujarat population. The provisional data shows that male and female were 112,976 and 113,793 respectively as per 2011 Census. The Dangs district is totally Scheduled Tribe [ST] area; about 94 percent population is the Scheduled Tribe in the district.⁴

Table 2: Demographic comparison of Dang district of year 2001 and 2011

Description	2001	2011
Total population	1,86,729	226769
Male population	93974	112976
Female population	92755	113793
ST population	158,456	216,073
Density (per sq. km.)	129	106
Sex ratio	987	1006
Child sex ratio	974	964
Child population (0 – 6 age)	36547	39387
Total literates	89,586	140,968
Female literates	36,247	63,654

(Source: Census of India 2001 and 2011)

³ District census handbook, The Dangs, 2011

⁴http://censusindia.gov.in/2011census/dchb/2422_PART_B_DCHB_THE%20DANGS.pdf

Education data and Analysis

Education facility in Dang district:

Table 3: Education facility in Dang district

Sr. No.	Level of School	2001	2011	2018
1	Primary school (Total)	268	308	378
	Primary (1 to 5)	162	173	256
	Primary (6 to 8)	106	135	122
2	Secondary school	11	16	22
3	Higher secondary school	5	7	8
	Commerce Stream	4	5	5
	Science + Commerce	1	2	3
4	College total	0	0	3
	Science college	0	0	1
	Commerce college	0	0	1
	Agriculture university	0	0	1
5	Industrial training institute	0	0	1

(Source: District education office, Ahwa – The Dangs)

Table 3 is showing decadal comparison of education infrastructure facility in the Dang district. As per data of 2018, it can be seen that there are total 311 anganwadi are available in the district. Total 378 primary schools are available in the district. Out of 378 primary schools 256 schools are running 1 to 5 standards and 122 schools are running 1 to 8 standards. Twenty two secondary schools are serving whole district. Only 8 higher secondary schools are available in the Dang district. Out of 8 higher secondary schools 5 schools are running commerce stream and 3 schools are running science and commerce schools. As it can be seen, there were no colleges are available in the decade of 2001 to 2011. As per status of 2018, there total 3 colleges are available in the Dang district. Out of them 1 is Science College, 1 is Commerce College and 1 is Agriculture University. Science and Commerce Colleges are in Ahwa taluka. Agriculture University is situated in Waghai taluka. One ITI centre is situated in Ahwa taluka.

Figure 3: Location wise secondary and higher secondary school in Dang district year 2018 (Source: Author)

Above figure is showing the location of the secondary schools, higher secondary school of the Dang district. As it can be seen that there total 8 secondary schools and 3 higher secondary schools are situated in Ahwa taluka. Total 5 secondary schools and 3 higher secondary schools are available in Waghai taluka. 5 secondary schools and 2 higher secondary schools are available in Subir taluka.

Figure 4: Colleges in Dang district (Source: Author)

Figure 4 is showing the location of colleges in Dang district. Total 4 colleges are available in district. One science and commerce colleges are situated in Ahwa taluka. One ITI centre is also located in Ahwa taluka. Agriculture university and research centre is situated in Waghai taluka.

Gap Analysis of the Education facility

Table 4: Gap Analysis

Dang district Population					228291	
Sr. No.	Level of School	As per norms Numbers	Population serving	Required in district	Existing	GAP
1	Primary School Total	1	2500	92	378	286
	Primary (1 to 5)				256	
	Primary (6 to 8)				122	
2	Secondary	1	7500	31	22	-9
3	Higher Secondary	1	15000	16	8	-8
	Commerce Stream				5	
	Science + Commerce				3	
4	College Total	1	125000	2	3	1
	Science College				1	
	Commerce College				1	
	Agriculture university				1	
5	ITI	1	100000	3	1	-2

Above table 4 is showing Gap analysis of the education facility at different level. As it showing the results, total 3 level of education levels are showing minus figure, which indicates that these facilities are lacking facilities. Total 9 secondary schools, 8 higher secondary schools and 2 industrial training institutes are required in whole district.

Suggestion & Recommendations

- After doing Gap analysis of the education facility, it is conclude that 9 secondary schools are recommended in the Dang district.
- Total 8 higher secondary schools are recommended in in whole district.
- This secondary schools and higher secondary schools can be established as per the required locations.
- Gap analysis is showing 2 ITIs' are lacking in the district. As one ITI is situated in Ahwa taluka 2 new ITIs' can be established in Waghai taluka and Subir Taluka.

References

- [1] Deshmukh, D. S. (2016). Primary Education in Dang district: A Study. *International Journal for Research in Education (IJRE)*, 1-5.
- [2] Rami, G. (2012). Status of Primary education: A case study of the Dang district in Gujarat. *IAMURE: International Journal of Education*, 41-63.
- [3] Urban and Regional Development Plans Formulation and Implementation (URDPFI) Guidelines, Volume 1, January 2015.
- [4] District census handbook, The Dangs, census 2011 & 2001.
- [5] Revenue record of government of Gujarat.